

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on new students' interest in college: case study: High school of economics in Makassar city

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Abstract

The world of education, which is a major need in developing the quality of human resources, also feels the presence of the corona virus. Universities have also been impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. Education as a very important aspect in the development of human resources must surrender and adapt to current conditions. For old students, of course, having to adapt to online or online lectures which some people agree is more difficult than offline lectures. This study looks at the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on student interest in studying at the College of Economics in Makassar City. To achieve the research objectives and provide answers to the problems posed, this research uses quantitative methods by taking cross-sectional data in the form of responses from universities, namely the College of Economics (STIE) in Makassar City. The online learning process is indeed a new thing in the world of Indonesian education where most of the teaching staff and students are still adapting to this condition. It is undeniable that this online learning process makes it easier for both teachers and students (students) to be able to carry out lectures anywhere and anytime. However, we also cannot deny that the ability to absorb material from each student is different. The contents of each student's glass are different from one another. There are students who absorb lecture material very easily, but there are also those who require more detailed explanations and even face-to-face explanations. So that the pandemic condition with the online learning process also affects students' interest in college. There are those who do decide to stay in college, as explained earlier, but there are also those who choose not to go to college first on the grounds that they cannot follow the online learning process.

Keywords: Education; Corona Virus; Learning Process; Student; Makassar City

1. Introduction

World moment this currently experiencing the Global Pandemic Corona Virus Disease-19 (COVID-19) as stated by the World Health Organization (WHO) on March 11, 2020. The COVID-19 pandemic has struck at least 214 countries including Indonesia and force more than half people man lock yourself inside _ house.

COVID 19 pandemic in Indonesia began with findings sufferer COVID-19 disease on the following March 2, 2020 impact on increasing number of victims and extent affected area coverage disaster, as well raises implications for broad socio - economic aspects in Indonesia. Until finally on April 13, 2020, the Government of Indonesia determined the status of a non- natural disaster to plague corona virus disease COVID-19 in with issuance of Presidential Decree (Kepres) Number 12 of 2020 concerning Spread of Corona Virus Disease (COVID -19) As National Disaster.

COVID-19 pandemic really has impact on the world of education in Indonesia. it _ resulted education level elementary and intermediate changed in a manner dr die only in time count day. Pandemic this has resulted in 404 thousand school closed in

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Indonesia. kindly national, more of 51 million participant educate from PAUD, SD, SMP, SMA, SMK, SLB out from room class. Sudden formal school forced to in a manner simultaneously use learning media applications distance far for students, no careful preparation, for the sake of replacing learning stare face in class. teachers by suddenly did _ something different _ in gift lesson to his students. Something's awkward with technology, as a result the teachers only give Duty every the day. So that students don't have flexibility time at home because many Duty given by the teachers.

However there are also capable teachers utilise moment pandemic this for increase potency benefit digital platform accessibility with make content typical e-learning learning, so student feel happy and comfortable in learn. However, capable teachers the still a little, no comparable with amount lots of students. Besides that there are also busy agencies make TV shows with serving learning to a degree that is important there is activity study online.

College height also accept impact from the COVID-19 pandemic. this pandemic of course impact on the whole aspect society. Education as very important aspect in development source power man must surrender and adapt with condition moment this. For Old student, of course must adapt with online or online lectures that are agreed upon by more people difficult than offline lecture. Student new faced with a dilemma want to continue education (enroll in college height) or postpone until condition returns to normal as a result limitations cost. Almost all college tall experience decline amount student new for class year 2020/2021.

Purpose and Benefits

- Study this aim for knowing impact from the COVID-19 pandemic to Interest Studying Student new.
- Study this beneficial for academics _ for the more enrich repertoire knowledge knowledge.

2. Theory

Paradigm in discipline intellectual is method people 's view themselves and their environment will affect it in thinking (cognitive), behaving (affective), and behaving behavior (conative). Paradigm too _ means set assumptions, concepts, values, and practices that are applied in looked reality in a the same community, in particular, within discipline intellectual

Education is effort conscious and planned for realize atmosphere learning and the learning process for participants educate in a manner active develop potency himself for have strength spiritual, religious, controlling self, personality, intelligence, morality glorious as well as the necessary skills himself, his community and nation. (National education system law chapter I, article 1) Paradigm education is something method see and understand education, and from corner view this our observe and understand problems education faced and sought _ method resolve problem the. And also deep education there is a number paradigm think. Paradigm behavioristic, constructivist and social cognitive possess _ influence in education.

Paradigm development is method view to something problem development used _ in maintenance development in the sense of development good as a process or as method for reach enhancement quality life people and well- being people. Economic development demanded for could Fulfill needs energy, food, transportation, clean water, sanitation, health, telecommunications, infrastructure in a sustainable manner (sustainable development), and accordingly principle fair (growth with distribution).

Indonesia 's economic development must increase power competitiveness and independence nation to leave as winner in global competition. Besides it is in the development process will demanded the more big in development progress knowledge knowledge and technology appropriate use (appropriate technology) in all aspect development economy. For support Vision 2025 The Government of Indonesia is also improving role development economy in relieve poverty and improve global prosperity at play as standard size development (basic need development).

According to Dictionary Major Indonesian (2001) in Fitriany (2008), interest that is trend high heart _ to something. Hurlock (1993) interest is source driving motivation _ somebody for To do what want _ conducted when free choose. When someone evaluate that something will useful, then will Becomes interested, then Thing the bring satisfaction. When satisfaction decrease so interest too _ decreased. So that interest no characteristic permanent, however interest characteristic temporary or could capricious. (www.profession.accountant/interest/understanding-interest.html).

According to Widayastuti, et al (2004) interest is desire driven by something _ desire after see, observe and compare as well as consider with the needs he wants. With so, can concluded that there is a number of necessary thing _ pay attention to interest this namely:

- Interest is influencing factors _ behavior someone.
- Interest show how much hard somebody brave try do something.
- Interest show how much many attempted effort _ somebody for To do something.
- Interest show how much like somebody to something.

2.1. Corona Virus Disease 2019

In term simple, launched from The Sun, COVID-19 is abbreviation from Corona (CO), Virus (VI) Disease (D) and the year 2019 (19), which is the corona COVID-19 virus first appeared in 2019. The World Health Organization (WHO) finally set COVID-19 for called the moderate corona virus epidemic around the world this Coronavirus is family big virus that can cause disease, start from the common cold until disease severe breathing, such as Syndrome Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) and Syndrome Respiration I Severe (SARS).

Since first time this virus detected in Wuhan, China, in December 2019, outbreak this has growing very fast. WHO ago label this COVID-19 corona virus outbreak as a global pandemic. Symptom typical of the COVID-19 corona itself including fever, cough, trouble breath, pain muscle until exhausted. In more cases _ seriously, this virus can cause severe pneumonia, syndrome disturbance respiration acute, sepsis and shock septic.

2.2. The Role of Education in Growth Economy

Education no could regardless from problem economy, fine in a manner direct nor no direct. Various study academic and research empirical has prove its validity. Alhumami (2004), stated education no only give birth to source power qualified human, have _ knowledge and skills as well as dominate technology, but also can grow climate healthy and conducive business _ for growth economy. it _ push every citizen for _ independent entrepreneurship in a manner fair and healthy. In other words, too as well as give contribution active in development through productivity could increase income as well as in the end jack up growth economy.

Studies about investigation source power man has conducted by Schultz (1961), argued that investigation source power man will capable increase quality source power that Becomes more productive and is one _ method for go out from slavery.

Increasing source power man will make man have more many choice, so will created enhancement welfare. A number of activities that according to Schultz can repair ability source power man is with through most have formal education connection tightly with enhancement ability source power human. Investment in the field education no only useful for individually, but also for group of people or community business as well as Public general.

Achievement education at all levels _ will increase income and productivity society. Education is Street going to progress and achievements social and economic welfare, meanwhile failure build education will give birth to various crucial problems: unemployment, crime, abuse drugs, and crime, abuse drugs, and the welfare defense that becomes burden social political for government.

3. Research methods

3.1. Subject Research

Study this try study condition college tall College of Science Tri Dharma Nusantara Economy in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic.

3.2. Instrument Research

In framework reach destination research and deliver answer on problem posed _ so study this use method quantitative with take cross-sectional data in the form of response from college tall ie College of Science Economics (STIE) Tri Dharma Nusantara Makassar.

Response the will obtained through surveys both online and non-online with method purposive sampling, that is method gift questionnaire to each STIE who is willing give response when contacted or visited. Questionnaire submitted _ mixed based on questions that have been plural used in analyze impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on interest studying students _ new. In given questionnaire, the questions asked _ will mixed such such as not raises impression researcher want to knowing more in the STIE conditions studied.

4. Results and Discussion

Based on Figure 1, as many as 89.1% of respondents is status student _ studying while work. Campus STIE Tri Dharma Archipelago of course have part big student which work while college. Most _ from they finance studying from salary earned. _ this seen from picture under where as much as 76.6% of students finance studying from salary and as much as 23.4% students finance studying from parents. See magnitude percentage working students while college, got said that student new have interest high school in the middle condition pandemic moment this especially part big student finance studying they alone from salary earned every month.

Figure 1 Student Status

Figure 2 Employment Status Student

Figure 3 Income Student If Working

Pandemic COVID-19 also impact on student which work while college. From Figure 2 it can be seen that as much 64.1% students still working, 25% students Been laid off and still are look for work, and 10.9% already get profession new.

Naturally pandemic situation that occurred moment this and yet is known when will end be a determining factor interest studying students, especially student which source financing his lecture originated from wages which they get. If in a manner suddenly they dismissed from profession so of course just will disturb continuity lectures they or with say other they will stop college. para student or respondent this is also not get scholarship from government.

Figure 4 Parents ' Income Student

Figure 5 Interested Learning Process

Based on figure 3, income students per month as much as 28.8% own income of IDR 500,000 – IDR 1,000,000, so on as much as 25.4% own income of IDR 1,000,001 – IDR 1,500,000, and as many as 16.9% of students each have income IDR 1,500,001 – IDR 2,000,000 and more from IDR 2,500,000. With income per month like on of course possible student for finance expenses per month including with pay cost studying where on the STIE Tri Dharma Nusantara campus apply pattern payment studying with method instalment for accommodate working students _ while college. Naturally when student finance studying with salary, then for internet quota for lectures borne by them alone. The students new this not yet get help quota learning from government.

Based on Figure 4 is visible that as much as 46.9% of parental income student IDR 500,000 – IDR 1,000,000, so on as much as 21.9% have income of IDR 1,500,001 – IDR 2,000,000, and as much as 14.1% have income as big more from IDR 2,500,001. With see proportion like this could said that working students _ while studying have interest studying which tall although income person old they no many. The students want to permanent continuing education in the middle pandemic conditions though must set aside part big income for finance studying them.

The initial pandemic condition started from problem health, enter year second this start penetrate to problem economic and social. Not a little employee must _ experience termination connection employment (layoff). Naturally Thing this impact on interest studying student at every college high. Conditions that are not erratic faced with costs partial lecture _ big they not quite enough alone of course be the determining factor biggest in continuing education for children _ nation.

From figure 5 can seen that as much as 84.4% of respondents say more like the learning process outside network (offline) and the rest as much as 15.6% of respondents more like the learning process in network (online). The online learning process indeed is Thing new in the world of Indonesian Education where of course part big power teacher and

student still Keep going adapt with condition this. Not denied that this online learning process more make it easy good power teacher nor participant educate (student) for could doing lectures where just and when just. However neither do we can deny that ability absorb Theory from each student different.

Like a glass, of course content glass every student different Among one and another. There are students who are very easy absorb Theory college, however some need _ explanation even more detail explanation in form stare face. So that pandemic conditions with the online learning process also affect interest studying student. There is indeed decide for permanent study, like explanation before, however some choose _ for no in college especially formerly with reason no can follow process learning in network (on line).

5. Conclusion

The condition of the COVID-19 Pandemic has caused students to study while working like a simalakama fruit. On the one hand, they are happy with the online learning process, but on the other hand they are less able to understand the subject matter. On the other hand, the threat of termination of employment is always haunting, considering that the condition of this pandemic has also caused a crisis on the economic side. From the perspective of parents' income, it can be said that students work part-time studying have interest studying which tall although income person old they no many. Students want to continue their education in the midst of a pandemic, even though they have to set aside a large portion of their income to pay for college they.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Everyone who participated in the study gave his or her informed consent.

References

- [1] Riani Nurainah Lisnasari, Fitriani. (2008). Influencing Factors _ Interest Student Accountancy for Participate in Professional Education Accounting.
- [2] Truna, Dody. S., 2013. Paradiga education quality. Jakarta: Faithful library.
- [3] Widyastuti, Suryaningsum and Juliana. 2004. Influence Motivation to Interest Student Accountancy For Participate in Professional Education Accounting. VII National Symposium on Accounting : Yogyakarta.